

Electrometric Titrations of Fulvic Acids from Soil Humus

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Fulvic acids isolated from four different soils were subjected to electrometric titrations, both conductometric and potentiometric, with caustic soda in presence and absence of sodium chloride. Baryta alone was also used for titration. On the basis of the breaks and inflexions in the titration curves the functional groups of the fulvic acids could be estimated. The fulvic acids from Palampur, Dehra Dun, and Jodhpur differed from that from Chinsura in having two breaks in the conductometric titration curves instead of three in the latter. The potentiometric titrations did not show significant variations. The titration curves of fulvic acids were compared with those of succinic, phthalic and salicylic acids as model substances. The base exchange capacities calculated from titrations with caustic soda, as also baryta varied from 690 to 1300 m.e./100 g for the different fulvic acids.

Humic acid in its acid form is an electrochemical system. Electrometric titrations of humic acids with different bases have been carried out by a number of investigators^{1,2}. The number of breaks in the curves as reported in the literature varies from one to four (*loc.cit.*). In some cases good correlation has been obtained between potentiometric and conductometric data (*loc.cit.*). The total acidity determined by conductometric titration is always greater than that determined by potentiometric method³. The end point can be determined much better with conductometric titration than with potentiometric titration of aqueous solutions¹.

Fulvic acid, the lowest molecular weight component of humus, is also likely to be an electrochemical system, and as such is amenable to study by means of electrometric titrations, i.e. conductometry and potentiometry. This study forms the subject matter of this paper.

Chemically, fulvic acid, the acid soluble and alkali soluble fraction of humic acid, has not been as thoroughly investigated as humic acid itself, and very little is known about its chemical nature. Forsyth⁴ found that the fulvic fraction of soil humus could be separated into four subfractions by means of a selective adsorption technique using charcoal as the adsorbent. These subfractions are A : the filtrate and washings (with 0.1*N* HCl) containing simple organic substances such as amino acids and sugars ; B: obtained by eluting the charcoal with 90% acetone containing

1. H. Van Dijk, *Sci. Proc. Royal Dublin Soc.*, 1960, 1, Series A, 163-176.
2. B. Chatterjee and S. Bose, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1952, 7, 414-427.
3. B. K. Seal, Thesis, University of Calcutta, 1963.
4. W. G. C. Forsyth, *Biochem. J.*, 1947, 41, 176.

phenolic glycosides ; C : eluted with distilled water containing polysaccharides having uronic acid groups ; and D : eluted with 0.5*N* caustic soda solution giving positive tests for pentose sugars and being rich in nitrogen and phosphorus.

Other investigations on the fulvic acid fraction have been reported by Ponomareva⁵ and Tiurin⁶. Ponomareva (loc.cit.) studied the properties of fulvic acids isolated from soil and found that they could be separated into one fraction precipitated by calcium or barium hydroxide and another not so precipitated. The latter fraction was lighter in colour and contained a greater percentage of carbon. She reported the equivalent weight of fulvic acid to be 160. Tiurin (loc.cit.) reported that fulvic acids were nitrogenous complexes of equivalent weight about 300. Bremner⁷ has shown that at least 20-30% of fulvic nitrogen is in the form of protein which has the amino acid composition. Recent work⁸ on the organic phosphorus of soil has shown the presence of inositol phosphates and nucleic acid derivatives in this fraction, a considerable fraction of its nitrogen being in the form of nucleic acids or nucleotides.

We have dealt in this paper with the fulvic acid fraction precipitated by barium hydroxide. The main purpose of the present investigation was to ascertain, as far as possible, the different acid groups and their relative proportions in soil fulvic acids by means of electrometric titrations. If fulvic acid is considered as a precursor of humic acid, as many believe, the functional groups contributing to acidity are —COOH and —OH groups.

The method of investigation was as follows : The colloidal solutions of fulvic acids were subjected to potentiometric (using glass electrode *pH*-meter) and conductometric (using Leeds-Northrup conductivity set) titrations against caustic soda and barium hydroxide. From the observed inflexions and bends the amount and nature of the acidic groups have been determined. It is assumed, as in humic acids¹, that the acid groups which have not reacted with a base at $pH \approx 7$ and above are phenolic hydroxyl groups and those neutralised at lower *pH* are carboxyl groups.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation and Separation of Soil Organic Matter : For the present work, one type of soil each from Dehra Dun, Palampur, Jodhpur and Chinsura has been selected. The descriptions as well as the organic matter contents of the soils as determined by the method of Walkley and Black⁹ are given below in tabular form.

5. V. V. Ponomareva, *Pochvovedenie*, 1947, 714 (S. F. 11, 300).
6. I. V. Tiurin, *Trans. Dokuchaev Inst.*, 1940, 23. 23 (S. F. 4, 185).
7. J. M. Bremner, *J. Sci. Food. Agric.*, 1952, 3, 497.
8. J. M. Bremner, *J. Soil Sci.*, 1954, 5, No. 2, 227.
9. M. L. Jackson, *Soil Chemical Analysis*, 1962, 219.

Soil	Short Description	Organic matter %
Dehra Dun	Barkot range, Altitude 660 m, Sal forest. Big stones and boulders in subsoil, sandy loam to sandy clay loam, plenty of roots, acidic and non-calcareous. Surface soil.	5.5
Palampur	Soil Testing Laboratory, Palampur, Kangra. Surface Soil. Village—Alma Bandla.	2.6
Jodhpur	Central Arid Zone Research Institute, Loam to sandy soil. Lime concretions at 100-150 cm. Surface soil.	0.26
Chinsura	Chinsura Rice Research Station, West Bengal Government Farm. Clayey and sticky, grey coloured, paddy lands. Surface soil.	0.67

Humus was extracted by treating the soil with 0.5N sodium carbonate solution, then allowing it to stand overnight and finally siphoning off the supernatant liquid containing sodium salts of humic and fulvic acids. This was centrifuged and the crude humic acid was precipitated from the centrifugate by acidifying with dil.HCl to pH 2-3 and freed from the supernatant liquid in the centrifuge. The yellow coloured supernatant liquid contained fulvic acid.

Purification of Crude Fulvic Acid: It has been observed that the fulvic acid in solution got slowly polymerised on standing. However, in the form of its barium salt it was more stable. Hence it was converted into its barium salt by treating the centrifugate with a solution of barium chloride and raising the pH to 7-8 with a dilute solution of caustic soda, when a brown coloured precipitate

of barium fulvate was obtained from a light straw yellow coloured supernatant liquid. The precipitate was at first dialysed against distilled water for nearly a

week and finally purified by mild electro dialysis. Fulvic acid was prepared fresh before each titration by passing the aqueous suspension of barium fulvate through a column of Amberlite IR-120 in the H-form and eluting the bed with water till the eluate that came through was colourless.

Conductometric Titrations: Continuous conductometric titrations were carried out with caustic soda and barium hydroxide solutions using a Leeds-Northrup conductivity bridge in a thermostat maintained at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. Usually twentyfive to thirty almost equally spaced additions of the bases covered the entire titration.

The conductometric titration curves (figs. 1—4) of fulvic acid with caustic soda and baryta (the latter not given in the figures) show two breaks in the case of fulvic acids from Dehra Dun, Palampur and Jodhpur soils, and three in the case of Chinsura soil, indicating respectively presence of two acid functions in the former

FIG 3
TITRATION CURVES OF 0.6 mg OF FULVIC ACID FROM DEHRADUN SOIL IN 40 ml. OF WATER.

Fig. 3(a) ●●● CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATION IN WATER WITH 0.05N NaOH (CONDUCTIVITY SCALE ON LEFT SIDE OF LEFT HAND ORDINATE)
Fig. 3(b) ○○ POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION IN WATER WITH 0.05N NaOH (PH SCALE)
Fig. 3(c) ○○ POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION IN WATER WITH 0.05N NaOH IN PRESENCE OF 1M NaCl (PH SCALE)

FIG 4.
TITRATION CURVES OF 0.2 mg OF FULVIC ACID FROM JODHPUR SOIL IN 40 ml WATER.

Fig. 4(a) ●●● CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATION IN WATER WITH 0.05N NaOH (CONDUCTIVITY SCALE ON LEFT SIDE OF LEFT HAND ORDINATE)
Fig. 4(b) ○○ POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION IN WATER WITH 0.05N NaOH (PH SCALE)
Fig. 4(c) ××× POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION IN WATER WITH 0.05N NaOH IN PRESENCE OF 1M NaCl (PH SCALE)

and three in the latter. Under almost comparable concentrations (7—8 mg/40 ml, table 1) the initial conductances of fulvic acid solutions are different. In the order of decreasing conductances the acids can be arranged as follows :

Chinsura > Palampur > Dehra Dun > Jodhpur. The features of the titration curves with the two bases showed little real difference. This is unlike the results obtained with humic acids¹⁰ which suggest a stronger acid character when titrated with baryta than when done with caustic soda.

TABLE 1

Fulvic acid from	Concentration in mg./40 ml	Specific conductance at ($\alpha=0$) $\times 10^6$ (mhos.)	Specific conductance at ($\alpha=1$) $\times 10^6$ (mhos)
Dehra Dun	8.6	36.0	30.7
Palampur	8.3	50.3	45.5
Jodhpur	8.2	28.4	29.0
Chinsura	7.0	63.2	67.3

All the conductometric titration curves show a pronounced initial drop in specific conductance and a sharp break amounting to about 10 to 55 percent neutralisation which corresponds, most likely, to reaction with the carboxyl groups associated with an aromatic ring. This point is confirmed by referring to the conductometric titration curves of salicylic, phthalic and succinic acids presented in fig. 5. Drawn on the same scale the titration curve of salicylic acid containing

a $-\text{COOH}$ and a phenolic $-\text{OH}$ group in the aromatic ring shows a sharper initial drop than that of phthalic acid containing two $-\text{COOH}$ groups in the aromatic ring. The titration curves of Palampur, Dehra Dun and Jodhpur fulvic acids are similar to that of salicylic acid, whereas that of Chinsura fulvic acid is similar to that of phthalic acid except that of a third break in the titration curves of Chinsura fulvic acid, which perhaps corresponds to the neutralisation of phenolic $-\text{OH}$ groups.

The neutralisable acidities (m.e./100 g.) corresponding to the breaks in the curves are given in table 2. The values obtained with baryta are generally higher

than those with caustic soda. The base exchange capacities calculated from the final breaks of the different fulvic acids are in the range 690 to 735, excepting

TABLE 2

Total Acidities of Fulvic Acids expressed in m.e./100 g.

Fulvic acid from	Conductometrically at			Potentiometrically at		
	1st break	2nd break	3rd break	1st inflex.	2nd inflex.	3rd inflex.
Palampur	240	690	—	305	700	—
Chinsura	260	830	1300	—	845	1310
Dehra Dun	245	735	—	300	735	—
Jodhpur	190	720	—	255	730	—

that from Chinsura soil which has got a much higher b.e.c. (1300 m.e./100 g.). These b.e.c. values (table 3), as may be seen by comparison with those given in

TABLE 3

Fulvic Acid from	Equivalent weight		B. e. c. in m. e./100 g.	
	Using NaOH	Using Ba(OH) ₂	Using NaOH	Using Ba(OH) ₂
Dehra Dun	136	135	735	740
Palampur	145	141	690	710
Jodhpur	139	137	720	725
Chinsura	77	76	1300	1320

literature for fulvic acids, are much higher, the published values lying between 335 to 625 m.e./100 g.

Potentiometric Titrations : The potentiometric titrations were carried out at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ with a Cambridge pH-meter equipped with Cambridge glass electrode and a saturated calomel electrode with an aqueous agar-salt bridge. The electrodes were checked before each titration with buffers of pH 4.0 and 6.98. Potentiometric titrations were carried out continuously with caustic soda in absence and presence of 1.0M sodium chloride. Baryta alone was also used.

In order to locate more accurately the inflexion points, differential curves (not shown) for each titration have been constructed separately. Such inflexion points are shown by arrows in the curves (figs. 1b—4b) and the acidities corresponding to them are given in table 2. In general the location of end points is somewhat more difficult in the potentiometric curves than those in the conductometric curves. The weak initial inflexion in the baryta titration is absent in the caustic soda titration. The base exchange capacities calculated from the baryta titration curves are higher than those from the caustic soda titration curves, as it is so in the case of conductometric titrations. It has been observed that the titration curves of soil fulvic acids are more pronounced in their features than those of synthetic fulvic acids and the base exchange capacities of the latter are in the region 600 to 1200 m.e. (unpublished work from this laboratory). The titratable acidity determined by the potentiometric method differs only slightly from that determined by the conductometric method.

For purposes of comparison the apparent pK_{av} values of soil fulvic acids were determined from the pH titration curves at 50% neutralisation. The apparent pK_{av} values (table 4) for soil fulvic acids in absence of electrolytes range from 4.10 to 5.75.

TABLE 4

Fulvic Acid from	Initial pH	pK_{av} (from the graph) at $\alpha=0.5$	pH at the equivalence point
Dehra Dun	3.41	5.75	8.10
Palampur	3.08	4.70	8.45
Jodhpur	3.37	5.65	9.15
Chinsura	2.62	4.10	9.60

The addition of salt lowers, as expected, the pK_{av} values from 3.4 to 4.0. It will be noted that the order of the pK_{av} values is in agreement with that of the initial pH values.

Normally potentiometric titration curves should reflect the conductometric titration curves, but such concurrence is not found in the case of fulvic acids studied here. All the curves have weak inflexion points in the first part of the curves. Very small changes in pH have been observed in the case of fulvic acid from Chinsura soil. Thus, the inflexions in the curves given in figs. 1(b), 3(b) and 4(b) are sharper than those in fig. 2(b).

The inflexions in the potentiometric titration curves in presence of 1M sodium chloride are somewhat more pronounced than in its absence. A similar observation has been recorded in the case of humic acids, where salts are known to suppress the polyelectrolyte character of humic acids¹⁰.

A similar state of affairs may be envisaged in the case of fulvic acids. It is also possible that in presence of electrolyte some of the acid groups, particularly the $-\text{COOH}$ groups, may take part in exchange reaction with Na^+ liberating free H^+ ions which cause the observed pH drop in the titration curves, and also a change in the nature of inflexion.

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